

**Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability
of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through
Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge
Solutions' Gains**

D6.2: Project Website

Lead Author: Panayiotis Klitou (eBOS)

**Funded by
the European Union**

Grant Agreement No.	101060294		
Project Acronym	XGain		
Project Title	Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge Solutions' Gains		
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions		
Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-COMMUNITIES-01-03		
Project Start Date	September 1 st , 2022	Project End Date	August 31 st , 2025
Project URL	xgain-project.eu		
Work Package	WP6 Impact Maximisation and Outreach		
WP Lead Beneficiary	eBOS		
Deliverable type ¹ Dissemination level ²	DEC PUBLIC		
Contractual due date	28 February 2023	Actual submission date	28 February 2023
Lead Author (s)	Panayiotis Klitou (eBOS)		
Contributors	Marios Sophocleous (eBOS), Christos Skoufis (eBOS)		
Internal reviewer(s)	Vasilis Kotsikoris (RAIN), Shvea Järvet (CAFA), Eirini Liotou (ICCS)		

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¹R: Document, report; DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc; DMP: Data management plan; ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

² PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C - EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
V0.1	28/11/2022	5	ToC	Panayiotis Klitou (eBOS)
V0.2	25/01/2023	100	Deliverable content completed	Panayiotis Klitou (eBOS)
V0.3	31/01/2023	100	Minor Corrections	Vasilis Kotsikoris (RAIN)
V0.4	08/02/2023	100	Minor Corrections	Shvea Järvet (CAFA)
V1.0	21/02/2023	100	Final draft	Panayiotis Klitou (eBOS)

XGain Consortium			
#	Participant Organisation Name	Short name	Country
1	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	ICCS	EL
2	BENCO BALTIC DOO ZA SAVJETOVANJE IUSLUGE	BENCO	HR
3	CAFA TECH OU	CAFA	EE
4	IKE KAPTEN KOOUTS	CAPT	EL
5	EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED	eBOS	CY
6	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW - EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK	EVILVO	BE
7	FUNDACIO PRIVADA I2CAT, INTERNET I INNOVACIO DIGITAL A CATALUNYA	I2CAT	ES
8	INCITES CONSULTING SA	INC	LU
9	INTRACOM SA TELECOM SOLUTIONS	ICOM	EL
10	RAINNO IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA	RAIN	EL
11	REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT FUND OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	RDFCM	EL
12	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
13	UAB ART21	ART	LT
14	ZENTRUM FUR SOZIALE INNOVATION GMBH	ZSI	AT
15	TELEFONICA INVESTIGACION Y DESARROLLO SA	TID	ES
16	Astrocast SA	ASTRO	CH
17	JONATHAN MICHAEL SMITH	JS	UK

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MS	Milestone
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
URL	Uniform Resource Locators

Executive Summary

The XGain project aims to promote sustainable, balanced, and inclusive development in rural, coastal, and urban areas by providing access to a comprehensive inventory of smart XG, last-mile connectivity, and edge computing solutions for relevant stakeholders such as municipalities, policymakers, farmers, foresters and their associations. The project's overall objective is to deliver a Knowledge Facilitation Tool to aid in business model development and decision-making in selecting technology ecosystems that increase systemic resilience and energy efficiency, contribute to climate mitigation, and reduce digital divides among different groups. This will be achieved by taking a multi-actor and practitioner-oriented approach and assessing the socio-economic and techno-environmental effects of the solutions.

The project website serves as the primary means of communication and dissemination, allowing target groups and stakeholders to access information about the project's development and outcomes, and understand the benefits and impact of digital connectivity solutions in rural areas. The site will feature all public dissemination materials, and provide relevant content such as news, videos, workshops and demonstrations, press releases, and publications for key stakeholders, engaging them with the project's goals. Additionally, the website will feature digital visualizations of the project's processes and results, making it accessible to a wider audience.

This deliverable report serves as an accompanying document to complement the launch of the XGain project's website, that contributes towards XGain's visual identity, and helps increase dissemination of the project's outputs. It outlines the methodology used for the design and launch of the website and elaborates on its various pages and features. The website for this project was designed with a focus on simplicity, clarity, consistency, control, and user-friendliness. It features a modern design, clear and detailed content, and an easy-to-use structure. The launch of the website also marked the completion of one of the first milestones of the project, MS2.

1 Introduction

The deliverable “D6.2 – Project Website” of the XGain project is part of “Work Package 6: Impact Maximization and Outreach” and refers to the development the project’s website that contributes towards XGain’s visual identity, and helps increase dissemination of the project’s outputs. The development of the project website, together with the social media, mark the accomplishment of one of the early milestones, “MS2: Launch of XGain Visual identification and virtual presence”, which was due in M3 of the project. The website was in fact developed in M2 (October 2022), marking from an early stage the web presence and visibility of XGain as part of the “online” project’s dissemination activity. The website is continuously being updated, and these updates will continue during the project lifecycle and until project completion at M36, August 2025.

To support knowledge dissemination and impact maximization, all public deliverables will be published on the project website after the final review by the European Commission reviewers. Additionally, the project’s website and its content will remain available for 3 more years after the conclusion of the project.

1.1 Mapping XGain Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map XGain Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed. Table 1 shows which Tasks of the project provide input to this deliverable.

Table 1: Adherence to XGain GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

XGain GA Component Title	XGain GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			

D6.2 Project Website

Deliverable description: “The project website is up and running”

TASKS			
Task 6.1 Dissemination, Communication and Capacity Building	At the very beginning of the project, the visual identity (logo, a set of graphic elements and images, templates for presentations and publications) based on the material of the proposal documents, and the project public website containing a portfolio of materials and contents, will be established in M03 (MS02) – the project website will be constantly updated with the	All chapters and sections	The deliverable describes the methodology followed for the design and launch of the project website and the website content, to meet the dissemination requirements specified in the Task 6.1 description.

	project's latest activities and outcomes, including the communication objectives, its main messages, the underlying communication principles, the communication channels and activities and the respective consortium partners' roles and responsibilities.		
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1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This document is outlined in 6 chapters, structured to appropriately present the methodology followed for the design of the XGain project's website, and its main content and features. The 6 chapters comprise:

Chapter 1 provides the Introduction of the report, to map the work presented in this deliverable to the overall project's objectives.

Chapter 2 provides the methodology and principles adopted for the construction and development of the website.

Chapter 3 describes the website's structure and content and what can be found on each of the pages.

Chapter 4 deals with the Privacy and Cookies Policies.

Chapter 5 discusses the online presence management and monitoring, including website administration and google analytics and website traffic.

Chapter 6 presents the conclusion of the deliverable.

References

2 Methodology for the project website’s construction and development

This section provides a detailed description of the XGain website that has been developed to serve as the visual identification and virtual presence of the project. It is a website that utilises state of the art web development technology and design, in order to deliver content-rich information to the site visitors. The XGain website is part of the dissemination activities undertaken for this project and can be accessed by the following link: <https://xgain-project.eu/>.

The addition and modification of the website content is managed by the project partner eBOS. Any content-related process is submitted to the Dissemination and Communication manager of XGain, RAINNO, who then provides all the relevant information to eBOS. The website update procedures, including editing, validating and publishing of the content, are handled by eBOS project manager, Panayiotis Klitou.

For implementing the XGain official website, user interface design principles, and GA requirements have been taken into account. XGain’s modern interface embeds the latest best practices in its design to achieve multi-browser and multi-device compatibility (including smartphone, tablet, desktop PC or laptop). Its interface is fully reactive, user-friendly, delivering content rich information to the visitor, and easy access to any website content. Both the design and implementation process follow a user-oriented approach, to build an interface that is well-organized and practical. The website has been appraised by partners both in terms of content and in terms of usability, following an expert-based evaluation according to Nielsen’s usability heuristics. The GUI Design Principles were adopted in the XGain website interface design and implementation, as outlined in Figure 1 below. [1]

Figure 1: GUI Design Principles for the XGain website design

HTML5 [2], CSS3, and JavaScript [3] technologies have been adopted during the implementation of the XGain website, to achieve a responsive result, cross browser functionality and multi device compatibility.

The colours chosen for the website's graphics are the green and blue, based on the project's logo and branding book. The visuals designed for the website are based on the concept of the XGain project, which is to connect the unconnected rural, coastal and urban areas by a range of connectivity and edge computing solutions. Therefore, the background visual of the Home page, and header background of all the other pages, show a remote area with a pole and infrastructure suggesting the presence of a connectivity option, to convey immediately the idea of the project the website visitor.

3 Website Content

3.1 Website Structure

Figure 2 presents diagrammatically the sitemap of the initial working version of the XGain website. Further to the pages outlined in the diagram, a pop-up window where visitors can subscribe to the XGain Newsletter appears when entering the Home page.

Figure 2: Structure of XGain website

3.2 Home page

The “Home page” of the XGain website is loaded as soon as a user clicks the website link in a web browser, with the pop-up window for the Newsletter subscription appearing first. The Home page design is based on the rationale of long-scrolling pages, so as to give website visitors an early experience of the website’s contents. By scrolling down the Home Page, the visitor can see the complete title of the project, a short description about the project, the project duration and number of partners, the main objectives, the expected results of the project, some links to navigate to other pages of the website, the consortium, and some contact details.

The header hosts the main navigation menu, as well as links to social media channels of the XGain project. The main navigation menu is consistently placed through all webpages at the top of the page, while the project logo also acts as a redirection to the home page.

Figure 3 below shows several screenshots of the “Home page” of the website upon scrolling from top to bottom of the page. The “Click it!” bottom right corner icon brings back the Newsletter Subscription pop-up window.

XGain

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Home | About | Dissemination & Communication | News & Events | Contact | Newsletter Subscription

Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge Solutions' Gains

XGain fosters a sustainable, balanced, and inclusive development of rural, coastal and urban areas by facilitating access to relevant stakeholders to a comprehensive inventory of smart XG, last-mile connectivity and edge computing solutions, and of related assessment methods. The XGain's project overall objective is to deliver a Knowledge Facilitation Tool, facilitating business model development, supporting decision-making in the selection of an ecosystem of technologies, consisting of connectivity options and edge processing solutions, by following a multi-actor and practitioner-oriented approach, and by coherently assessing their socio-economic and techno-environmental effects.

[Read More](#)

36 Months

X-Gain is a 3-year long EU-funded Research and Innovation Action starting 1st September 2022

17 Partners

The XGain consortium comprises of 17 organisations from 9 EU members, 2 associated members from UK & Switzerland respectively

Objectives

- #### 1

To empower public participation and multi-actor approach in transition towards enhanced sustainability design, social acceptance and fair solutions, through the interactive identification of end users' needs and co-creation of XGain system and Use Cases requirements.
- #### 2

To design and deliver a user-centric, interoperable and easy-to-use knowledge facilitation tool, for supporting actors of rural and coastal communities in their decision-making process on internet connectivity and edge technology options with appropriate operational business models.
- #### 3

To develop, establish and facilitate the selection of the most appropriate innovative business models that will include systemic level and cross-sectoral approaches.
- #### 4

To validate the outcome of the Knowledge Facilitation Tool in 6 unique fields with different technical, environmental, societal and economical structures and needs.
- #### 5

To develop, establish and facilitate the selection of the most appropriate innovative business models that will include systemic level and cross-sectoral approaches.

[Click it!](#)

Figure 3: XGain website Home page

3.3 The “About” page

The “About” page of the website contains icon links to navigate to the other subpages of the “About” page, including the “Concept & Methodology” page, the “Objectives” page, the “Consortium” page, and the “Use Cases in Living Labs” page. Also, the “About” menu in the header is a drop-down menu that also includes options to navigate to those subpages.

3.3.1 The “Concept and Methodology” page

Under the “Concept and Methodology” page, the user can read more on the background concept and motivation upon which the XGain project is based, as well as its core ambition. Following that, the methodology of the project is outlined within with the four different phases of the work, and the key services that the XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool will provide are listed.

3.3.2 The “Objectives” page

The “Objectives” page presents the five main objectives of the project, which can also be found on the Home page.

3.3.3 The “Consortium” page

The “Consortium” page includes information about the project coordinator, ICCS, and partners. The consortium partners are categorized based on the organization’s type, i.e., Research Technology Organizations, SME Partners, Governmental Organizations, and Large Industrial Partners. The partner’s logo and name are presented, and by clicking on the logo or name, a pop-up window appears where the user can read more information about the specific organization. By clicking on the arrow sign “>”, the user will be navigated to the official website of each partner. This is not only useful for the partners to be prominently displayed and easily accessible, but it also helps with the search engine optimization (SEO) of the XGain website. This means that the XGain results can reach a wider audience, as they will be more easily discoverable through search engines. The “Consortium” page is shown in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: The "Consortium" page of the XGain website

3.3.4 The "Use Cases in Living Labs" page

The "Use Cases in Living Labs" page begins by giving an overview of how the XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool will be demonstrated in the different Use Cases, and a map of the different locations of the Living Labs is shown. Following that, more details are given specifically for each of the six Use Cases. Photographs that describe the location or technology to be used at each location, are shown for each Use Case. The name of the sector where the tool will be validated and the location for each Use Case is given in a black "accordion" box. The user can click on the box and a drop-down panel appears giving more information about the Use Case. Figure 5 shows the structure of the "Use Cases in Living Labs" page.

e-newsletters will provide a snapshot of the main activities and achievements of the project, whereas broadcasting messages to a target pool of contact points via email is a highly effective measure of engagement, especially when promoting events and outcome among different domains. Newsletters will also be published on the website.

The content of these pages will be updated during the project, with the relevant dissemination material as soon as it is produced. Currently, the Brochures & Flyers page contains the XGain Project Banner and the Project Logos, and the Newsletter page contained the first release of Newsletter.

3.5 The “News & Events” page

Under this page, the visitor can see all the news about the project, the important meetings etc. This section of the website will be constantly updated according to the activities of the project. At the moment the visitor can read the first press release of the project, which concerns the Kick-off Meeting (KOM) of the project in Athens, in October 2022, and a Welcome Note by the Project Coordinator. By clicking on a post, the user is directed to the page with the whole text and photographs.

3.6 The “Contact” and “Newsletter Subscribe” pages

In the “Contact” page, the user can find the official email of the project (info@xgain-project.eu) and links to the social media, including LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, and YouTube. Furthermore, a contact box titled as “Let’s get in touch” is available, where the users can fill in their name, email and message. The user has to acknowledge that the data provided will be processed only for the purpose of examining the submitted question, and will not be released in any way, complying with the GDPR policy. The message is delivered to the eBOS’ project manager’s email who manages the website, and can reply back directly to the user’s email.

In the “Newsletter Subscription” page, the user can subscribe to the project’s newsletter by providing their name and email. The subscription box, as well as the subscription pop-up window that appears on the Home page, are connected to a Mailchimp form, which stores a mailing list of the users that subscribe to the Newsletter. These users will be emailed the Newsletter when one is released.

4 Privacy Policy and Cookies Policy

This section refers to the privacy policy and cookies policy compliance of the XGain project’s website. At the bottom of the Home page, an “Accept Cookies” option is available when loading the website for the first time, as shown in Figure 6. These options can be customized by the user by choosing the “Customize” option, or modified at any time by clicking the blue cookie at the bottom left of the page. This is powered by the WordPress General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Cookie Compliance plugin “CookieYes”. [4] The entire policy which is in alignment with the EU GDPR can be found at the bottom of the Home page by clicking on the tabs “Cookies Policy” and “Privacy Policy”. [5] These are publicly available in the following URLs and accessible from the Home page:

- Privacy Policy: <https://xgain-project.eu/privacy-policy/>
- Cookies Policy: <https://xgain-project.eu/cookies-policy/>

Figure 6: XGain website - Cookies policy

5 Online presence management and monitoring

5.1 Website administration

This section describes the administration site of the XGain website. The website has been built using WordPress (version 6.1.1). [6] WordPress is an open-source content management system widely used for website designs with emphasis on accessibility, performance, security, and ease of use. WordPress is GDPR compliant and offers a large database of plugins to be used, which are always updated with new trends and user friendly. The WordPress platform is hosted by SiteGround, a full-service web hosting company. WordPress is the first Content Management System worldwide that also gives the opportunity to the user to custom the content by using a variety of free templates and functionalities. [7]

Figure 7 below illustrates the welcome/main page that is displayed once the administrator logs in to WordPress. The navigation menu (on the left of the website) helps the administrator easily navigate through the different categories of the XGain website.

Figure 7: WordPress main page

WordPress version 6.1.1 offers a simple interface where the administrator can create a new page, rename a page or delete an existing page along. It includes features such as scheduling posts for some time in the future or backdating posts, saving drafts and previewing pages before publishing.

The administrator can view the page, and change the title of an existing page by choosing the “Quick Edit” option and they may also add a new page by choosing “Add New” on the top of the page. It is also feasible to see and edit the “Menu items” and “Menu Structure” by choosing “Appearance” and “Menu” from the left navigation bar. Figure 8 shows the Pages menu.

Figure 8: WordPress - Edit pages menu

The administrator can edit the content of a new or an existing page, by choosing “Pages” and “Edit with Elementor” option. “Elementor” is a WordPress page builder which works with all plugins and allows the creation of well-designed and fully-functional pages. [8] Figure 9 shows how the “Consortium” page is edited with Elementor.

Figure 9: WordPress - Edit with Elementor

5.2 Google Analytics & Website traffic

Google Analytics is a free web analytics service offered by Google that tracks website traffic and reports a variety of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) offering interesting insights about the website performance. [9] XGain website is registered in Google Analytics which offers a vast number of reports to satisfy even the more demanding web masters. Figure 10 provides a sample screenshot of the XGain Google Analytics, as generated for the period 01 September 2022 – 20 February 2023, presenting an audience overview information such as:

- Number of sessions, users and page views;
- Unique website visitors, Average session duration and pages viewed per session;
- Users’ activity (in the last 30 minutes, real-time, by time of day, etc.).
- Website visitor Sources;
- Demographic statistics (e.g. Users by country, city, language);
- Users that accessed the webpage using different devices (desktop and mobile).

Updated website “traffic” and more detailed analytics related to “Dissemination, Communication and Capacity building” will be presented in future deliverables, D6.3 and D6.4, that will be submitted on M18 and M36.

Figure 10: Google Analytics for the XGain website

6 Conclusions

This document serves as an accompanying report to complement Deliverable 6.2 and the launch of the XGain Project website. It outlines the methodology used for the design and launch of the website and elaborates on its various pages and features.

The website was designed based on the principles of clarity, comprehensibility, consistency, control, efficiency and simplicity. These principles are manifested through the website's modern design, rich and clear content of the pages, and user-friendly structure. The website's privacy policy is in alignment with the EU GDPR policy. The google analytics feature enables monitoring of the website's performance as a means to verify that the required KPIs regarding Dissemination and Communication, as far as the website is concerned, are met.

The launch of the project website fulfilled the accomplishment of MS2 for the project, serving as the core source of information about the project's objectives and activities, as well as contributing to the project's impact maximization and dissemination. The website will be constantly updated with the project's latest activities and outcomes, including the communication objectives, its main messages, the underlying communication principles, the communication channels and activities and the respective consortium partners' roles and responsibilities.

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